

INNOVATIVE ENTREPRENEURSHIP STRATEGIES FOR A DISRUPTIVE ERA

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Abstract

The Covid-19 pandemic that has ravaged the past two years and the technological advancements in this disruptive era have played a crucial role in the transformative changes brought about by new discoveries and innovations, necessitating the utilization of information technology in their development. The majority of sectors in the economy experienced instability during the pandemic, with the micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs). This research aims to explore aspects related to MSME business strategies. It employs a qualitative and descriptive research methodology, with the founders/owners of MSMEs as the research subjects. The data collection methods employed include interviews, observations, and documentation, enabling a comprehensive exploration of the subject matter. The research findings validate that digital marketing in the disruptive era facilitates MSMEs in providing information and engaging in direct interaction with consumers, expanding their market reach, and enhancing awareness and sales for these enterprises.

Keywords: Business Strategy, MSMEs, Disruptive Era, Entrepreneurship.

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INTRODUCTION

Micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) play a significant role in the GDP of the country. Understanding the importance of MSMEs and their substantial contribution to the national economy calls for strategic measures from the government to mitigate the negative impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on MSMEs. The government has implemented assistance programs for MSMEs through the Ministry of Finance, such as the National Economic Recovery Program (PEN) with a total budget of 123.47 trillion rupiahs. Additionally, through the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy, the government has introduced several programs aimed at revitalizing the economy through various recovery strategies, empowering tourism and creative economy stakeholders. However, as of March 2021, approximately 30 million MSMEs have experienced bankruptcy due to the COVID-19 pandemic, resulting in 7 million workers in the MSME sector losing their jobs. This situation necessitates strategic considerations to aid the economic recovery of the MSME sector.

This article aims to propose an approach within a strategic framework by providing stimuli to support the recovery of MSMEs. The research objective is to identify strategies that can be implemented by MSMEs to sustain themselves in the post-COVID-19 era. Conducting research on the role of MSMEs in supporting the Indonesian economy amidst the COVID-19 pandemic is crucial because micro, small, and medium enterprises play a strategic role in driving the national economy's growth in the post-pandemic aftermath.

In 2019, data released by American media company Wearesocial.com revealed that out of the total population of Indonesia, which amounted to 268.2 million, approximately 355.5 million or 133% were mobile phone users. Other findings indicated that the usage of mobile phones or smartphones reached around 90%, while the usage of computers or laptops was only about 20%. In line with this, the data also highlighted the digital platform activities, particularly e-commerce activities, where online buying and selling transactions were predominantly conducted through mobile phones, accounting for 76%, compared to only 37% on computers. This presents an opportunity that needs to be capitalized on by micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs).

Micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) are trade enterprises managed by individuals or legal entities, which fall under the criteria of small or micro-scale businesses. The regulations regarding MSMEs have been discussed in Law Number 20 of 2008. Many MSME activities utilize information technology to run their businesses. The increasing number of competitors becomes a consideration for business owners to innovate in order to thrive in the competitive landscape.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Fader (2012), the 1990s were the decade of e-commerce, and the early 21st century marked the era of social commerce. The role of "digital marketing" is confirmed by IBM's research, which includes interviews with CMOs (IBM Institute for Business Value, 2011). WSCs articulate the following four major challenges: data explosion (sometimes referred to as big data), social media, channel proliferation, and changing consumer demographics. Three out of the four major challenges are related to the development of digital marketing (Fader & Winer, 2012).

According to Kung, technological changes and consumer behavior have always been key factors in transforming media strategies (L. Kung, Strategic management in the media: Theory to practice (Jung, 2009). However, how these elements differ and, therefore, complex. It is important to have a clear understanding of what we mean by "digital marketing."

The Institute of Digital Marketing (DMI) defines digital marketing as "the use of digital technologies to create integrated, targeted, and measurable communications that help acquire and retain customers in building deeper relationships with them" (J. D. Chalmers et al., 2021). Simply put, digital marketing defines the term as follows: "Digital marketing is a subfield of traditional marketing that uses modern digital channels to host products, such as downloadable music, and primarily to communicate with stakeholders, such as customers and investors, about the brand, products, and business progress." Both definitions are useful; the first one highlights the importance of a strategic framework for any marketing approach, i.e., measurability and integration, as well as its focus on relationships and communication.

The second definition serves as a reminder that any use of digital marketing must be effective in promoting products or services, as well as encompassing good intellectual and communication strategies. It is also useful to clarify the meaning of other terms used in this

document. The term "creative industry" is commonly understood to encompass publishing, media (such as television and radio), architecture, crafts, and design, fashion, advertising, public relations, and computer games and software as defined by the US Department of Culture and Media Sport (Royle, J. and Laing, 2014).

Our position has implications for learning aspects in the broad field of small business and entrepreneurship research. For instance, certain domains in the field have advanced particularly in high-level research activities and knowledge accumulation, such as finance and new venture creation, and we may expect more theoretical advancements if the empirical groundwork is established. In less developed areas, such as ethics, social inclusion, and gender, there may be more room for engaging in empirical research to establish a foundation for specific conceptualizations of small businesses and theoretical developments. We offer suggestions for how these areas may evolve. Therefore, while debating against setting boundaries in terms of research agendas, we conclude that this is not a manifesto for a thousand blooming flowers or unfocused and poorly executed empiricism.

We subscribe to the position that knowledge is not objective, and all empirical studies have some theoretical assumptions, whether consciously or otherwise (Davidsson, 2005). One hindrance in the field to developing a strong conceptual foundation is the pressure to be 'real-world,' which has led to a failure to question many unquestioned assumptions. The field also suffers from a positive ideological bias that often goes unquestioned in entrepreneurship and small business literature. This particularly occurs when practitioners' interests seek evidence to promote the involvement of economic activity modes. Some scholars have already highlighted this.

For instance, questions the assumptions of much entrepreneurship literature, particularly those originating from the US, as being 'discriminatory, gender-biased, ethnocentric, and ideologically driven'. The Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) could also be described as having a committed ideological foundation for promoting entrepreneurship and assumptions about the relationship between business start-ups and economic growth (Bosma & Harding, 2007). There are also assumptions about who the real entrepreneurs are. The authors criticize the notion of entrepreneurship as an "individualistic exercise," but this is a response to years of acceptance in the field (Drakopoulou et al., 2007). Unfortunately, the extent to which researchers question such accepted assumptions still leaves much to be desired.

Related to this is the methods used in the field, with some reluctance by researchers to go beyond both functionalist paradigms and quantitative approaches. With functionalism, we refer to a worldview with an objectivist perspective rooted in regulation. This approach is often accepted without much reflection by researchers (Blackburn & Kovalainen, 2009).

The first gap in the literature relates to the role of entrepreneurial universities in responding to the needs of their stakeholders during disruptions such as the 2008 financial recession and the current COVID-19 pandemic. According to stakeholder theory (Venkataraman, 2002; Freeman et al., 2010), it is expected that all core entrepreneurial activities of universities (teaching, research, and entrepreneurship) should be adapted based on their vision and ability to engage

multiple stakeholders' needs as well as respond to external changes (Guerrero et al., 2020a). Little is known in the academic literature about how entrepreneurial universities respond to stakeholder needs before, during, and after external disruptions such as financial crises, natural disasters, or pandemics (Guerrero et al., 2020b).

Considering the digital disruption approach, the literature acknowledges that organizations need to generate agile responses to capture 21st-century opportunities through new businesses and innovative models (Nambisan et al., 2017). In this view, entrepreneurial universities are already recognized as responsible for technological disruption, entrepreneurship, and innovation (Guerrero et al., 2020a).

Venture Capital (VC) is a form of financing that focuses on investing in high-risk, high-potential-growth small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) that may have limited or no transaction history and are often overlooked by traditional sources of funding. VC plays a crucial role in fostering innovation and supporting the growth of these entrepreneurial ventures.

The development of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has had a significant impact on the VC industry. One explanation for this transformation is the increased efficiency that ICT brings to the financial system. ICT enables the collection, storage, and analysis of vast amounts of information, allowing VC firms to make more informed investment decisions. The availability of real-time data, advanced analytics, and digital platforms has streamlined the due diligence process, making it more efficient and reducing the time and resources required to evaluate potential investments.

Furthermore, ICT has facilitated entrepreneurship by providing tools and platforms that enable entrepreneurs to access information, resources, and networks necessary for starting and growing their businesses. Digital platforms, such as crowdfunding platforms and online marketplaces, have democratized access to capital, allowing entrepreneurs to raise funds from a broader pool of investors. These platforms also enable entrepreneurs to showcase their ideas, products, and services to a global audience, expanding their reach and market opportunities.

The use of ICT in VC has also transformed the nature of information exchange and collaboration within the industry. VC firms heavily rely on informal networks and relationships to source investment opportunities, gather market intelligence, and share knowledge. ICT has facilitated the creation of online communities, forums, and social networks where investors, entrepreneurs, and experts can connect, collaborate, and exchange information. These digital ecosystems have accelerated the flow of information, enabling VC firms to identify promising investment opportunities, access specialized expertise, and engage in collaborative due diligence processes.

However, it is important to note that the adoption of new technologies can also introduce uncertainties and challenges for entrepreneurs. The rapid pace of technological advancements and the changing digital landscape may create a sense of uncertainty and complexity, making it challenging for entrepreneurs to navigate and adapt to the evolving business environment. Nonetheless, when embraced and effectively utilized, these new technologies can enhance entrepreneurs' capabilities and reduce uncertainty, increasing their chances of success.

In conclusion, the development of ICT has had a profound impact on the VC industry. The increased efficiency and facilitated entrepreneurship brought about by ICT have transformed the way VC operates. The use of digital platforms, real-time data, and online communities has enabled VC firms to make more informed investment decisions, access a wider pool of entrepreneurs, and collaborate more effectively. However, it is crucial for entrepreneurs to continuously embrace and adapt to technological advancements to remain competitive in the disruptive era. Venture capitalists (VCs) heavily rely on pre-investment information to avoid adverse selection and post-investment information to avoid moral hazard (Wright and Robbie, 1998). They invest in high-risk small and medium enterprises (SMEs) with high growth potential but little or no transaction history, and other financial sources are more reluctant to provide resources to such ventures. For this reason, such private investments involve more due diligence and monitoring than other financing alternatives (Carey, 1993). ICT has facilitated information gathering for industry selection, company selection, deal origination, monitoring, and exit processes. The increased efficiency view sees ICT as a tool to make the VC process more efficient.

The entrepreneurial mechanism is the emergence of digital entrepreneurship facilitation in the flow of deals to VC industries. ICT has accelerated the process of creative destruction of Schumpeter, in which the demise of some traditional industries creates many new ones. This happened after the internet boom in the 1990s and also the web 2.0 which resulted in greater user innovation, bottom-up entrepreneurship, and crowdfunding platforms (Aldrich, 2014).

On the contrary, new technologies can increase the perceived environmental uncertainty for entrepreneurs, thus inhibiting their tendency to create new ventures or modify existing ones. However, when adopted, these new technologies can help entrepreneurs enhance their knowledge apparatus and thus increase their opportunities to develop entrepreneurial processes where opportunities are transformed into economic activities that create value. In this case, technology can prove beneficial in reducing contextual uncertainty (D. Chalmers et al., 2021). On the one hand, new technologies represent sources of uncertainty (McMullen & Shepherd, 2014); however, on the other hand, they can drive entrepreneurs to capture new opportunities ahead of incumbent firms (Obschonka & Audretsch, 2020).

These technological advancements are reshaping the entrepreneurship landscape. It is crucial for businesses to foster a digital transformation culture that is oriented towards continuous transformation. New technologies and their developments create many new opportunities for entrepreneurs to enhance their capabilities in managing new business models and improving their performance, leverage, and competitiveness (Fossen & Sorgner, 2021). It is relevant to examine the factors that assist entrepreneurs in embracing new technologies and using them creatively and openly as the basis for their ventures. We suggest that the dynamics of entrepreneurial business are heavily influenced by new technologies, and indeed, it is important to understand their evolution in the context of digital transformation. Therefore, it is important to explore the evolution and daily activities of entrepreneurs to explain the effects of adopting these new technologies.

Research conducted by (Lovendra, 2021) on the Influence of Augmented Reality Marketing on Buying Behavior of Maybeline Official Shop's Beauty Products on Shopee with Consumer Engagement as an Intervening Variable. The results of this study show that Augmented Reality Marketing has a significant influence on consumer engagement and buying behavior.

METHODOLOGY

The criteria that can be used in selecting informants phenomenologically in the research include direct experience of situations or events related to the research topic (Abdurahim et al., 2015). In this study, there were three informants selected using snowball sampling. The aim was to gain an understanding from the primary perspectives, where informants could a) describe the phenomenon they had experienced, especially in its nature and meaning, b) be willing to engage in lengthy research activities, c) be willing to be interviewed and recorded during the interviews or research, and d) provide consent for the publication of research findings.

The approach used in this study was phenomenology. Sweetman et al. (2010) explained it as a research strategy in which the researcher identifies the human nature of lived experience about a particular phenomenon. The research was conducted in the city of Makassar, focusing on the UMKM sector. This study used a qualitative method with a triangulation model, combining interview and observation methods for UMKM actors. Qualitative research aims to obtain a holistic understanding of the research object according to what is being studied. Qualitative research is concerned with the perceptions or opinions of the individuals under investigation and cannot be measured numerically.

Figure 1: Research Flow

The focus of this research is on how entrepreneurship utilizes strategies or actions to thrive in the disruptive era. It also investigates the problems and delimits the scope of the research. The primary data source for this research is data collected directly by the researcher from sources that possess the relevant information or data.

As a comparison, the secondary data source for this research is the findings from literature review regarding consumption theory. Field data is the type of data used in this research as it is collected directly from the field. Additionally, without a doubt, the library of data is utilized. In this research, interviews, observations, and documentation techniques are employed to gather data. Interviews are a meeting where two individuals gather to exchange information and ideas through questions and answers to contribute. Observations are a data collection method that produces written notes directly from the informants, the owners of micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs).

Analyzing the data in detail using data coding is an essential technique in qualitative research. Coding involves the process of categorizing and labeling segments of data based on their content, meaning, or relevance to the research questions. It helps to identify recurring patterns, themes, or concepts that emerge from the data. Researchers may use coding schemes or develop new codes as they progress through the analysis.

Coding allows for a systematic and structured analysis of the data, enabling researchers to derive meaningful interpretations and insights. Using coding to describe the data involves organizing the coded segments into meaningful categories or themes. Researchers describe and interpret the data based on the patterns and connections identified through the coding process. This step helps to establish a coherent narrative and provide evidence to support the research findings.

Overall, the documentation method and the subsequent data analysis techniques described above are integral to qualitative research. They allow researchers to delve into the richness and complexity of the collected data, uncover underlying meanings and patterns, and generate new knowledge and insights.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The interviews with the informants focused on MSMEs in the city of Makassar. Technological advancements have developed according to needs, especially in marketing, where social media and marketplaces provide convenience for MSME players, particularly in expanding their market reach.

From the three MSMEs that served as informants in this study from various industry categories, the entrepreneurs stated that using digital marketing helped them thrive online. From the interview results of each informant, it can be concluded that each informant, as explained above, has their own experiences in using digital marketing platforms to promote their products. Digital marketing has the potential to assist MSME players in selling their products.

Table 1: Study Informants

No	Name of Owner	Name of Business	Location and Type of Business
1.	Arfan	Black White Coffee	Jalan Pelopor Kemerdekaan/coffee shop Jalan
2.	Irsyad Adi Putra	Fatea	Pajaiang/coffee shop
3.	Ilham Maulana	Brother Foodie	Jalan Taman Sudiang/culinary

Source: Field observation data, 2023

Product Marketing

Digital marketing encompasses various online channels, platforms, and tools that businesses utilize to promote their products or services to a wide audience. It leverages the power of the internet and digital technologies to reach and engage with consumers effectively.

One of the key aspects of digital marketing is the ability to initiate and circulate information about consumer products or brands through social networks. Social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and TikTok have become essential marketing channels for businesses. These platforms allow businesses to create brand profiles, share content, and interact with their target audience. They provide spaces where businesses can showcase their products, post engaging visual content, share user-generated content, and run targeted advertising campaigns.

Instant messaging platforms also play a significant role in digital marketing. Messaging apps like WhatsApp, WeChat, and Facebook Messenger enable direct communication between businesses and customers. They provide an avenue for personalized interactions, customer support, and even transactional activities like order placements or inquiries. Digital marketing offers several advantages over traditional marketing methods. It allows businesses to reach a larger audience, target specific customer segments, and measure the effectiveness of their marketing campaigns in real-time. Digital platforms provide valuable data and insights into consumer behavior, allowing businesses to refine their marketing strategies and optimize their efforts for better results.

Furthermore, digital marketing offers greater flexibility and cost-effectiveness compared to traditional marketing channels. Businesses can choose from a variety of digital marketing tactics, such as search engine optimization (SEO), pay-per-click (PPC) advertising, content marketing, influencer marketing, email marketing, and social media advertising. Each tactic can be tailored to suit the unique goals and target audience of a business, ensuring maximum impact and return on investment. In summary, digital marketing encompasses a wide range of online channels and platforms that enable businesses to promote their products or services effectively. From social media platforms to instant messaging apps, these digital channels provide spaces for businesses to interact with consumers, share information, and build brand awareness. By leveraging the power of digital marketing, businesses can reach a larger audience, engage with customers on a more personal level, and achieve their marketing objectives in the digital era.

Product Marketing on Digital Platforms

The use of digital platforms for product marketing has become increasingly crucial for businesses in today's digital age. Arfan from Black White Coffee emphasizes the importance of utilizing social media, particularly Instagram, as a means to introduce their products to a wider audience (interviewed on March 15, 2023). By leveraging Instagram's visual nature and large user base, businesses can showcase their products through attractive images and engaging content. This allows them to generate interest and awareness among potential customers who may not have been reached through traditional marketing methods.

Irsyad Adi Putra from Fatea also recognizes the significance of digital platforms for his business (interviewed on March 25, 2023). He highlights that online or offline order offerings through digital platforms can greatly expand his market reach. By utilizing digital platforms, businesses can transcend geographical limitations and cater to a broader customer base. This opens up opportunities for growth and increased sales, as customers can conveniently access and purchase products regardless of their physical location.

Moreover, digital platforms provide convenience for both businesses and customers. As mentioned in the adapted interview from Ilham Maulana (April 5, 2023), businesses can promote their products even when physically unavailable. This means that potential customers can access information about the products at their own convenience, without relying on the presence of the business owner or sales personnel.

In addition to convenience, digital platforms offer various tools and features that enhance product marketing efforts. Businesses can leverage social media analytics to gain insights into their audience's preferences and behavior, enabling them to tailor their marketing strategies accordingly. They can also utilize features like hashtags, geotagging, and influencer partnerships to increase their reach and visibility on digital platforms.

Overall, digital platforms have transformed the way businesses market their products. By utilizing social media, online marketplaces, and other digital channels, businesses can reach a larger audience, expand their market, and promote their products effectively. The convenience, flexibility, and wide array of marketing tools provided by digital platforms have made them indispensable for businesses in their product marketing endeavors.

Ease of Market Identification on Digital Platforms

The interviews with Fatea, Black White Coffee, and Brother Foodie owners highlight the ease of market identification on digital platforms and its attractiveness for entrepreneurs. The owner of Fatea emphasizes that remote access on digital platforms is effortless and attracts many entrepreneurs (March 25, 2023). This ease of access allows entrepreneurs to reach a wide range of potential customers, expanding their market and increasing their chances of success.

Arfan, the owner of Black White Coffee, acknowledges that digital platforms like Instagram enable more partners to become familiar with his business (interviewed on March 15, 2023). Through digital platforms, businesses can showcase their products to a larger audience, attracting potential partners for collaborations or distribution opportunities. This increased

exposure and accessibility make it easier for businesses to connect with potential partners and expand their network.

Furthermore, Irsyad Adi Putra from Fatea highlights the significant benefits of using digital platforms for product marketing (March 25, 2023). He mentions that digital platforms provide an avenue for businesses to market their products effectively while enjoying the convenience of easier access. By leveraging digital platforms, businesses can establish their presence, engage with customers, and promote their products without the limitations of traditional marketing channels. This flexibility and accessibility contribute to the success of their marketing efforts.

Ilham Maulana, the owner of Brother Foodie, supports the idea that better connections and collaborations with marketplaces can be facilitated through digital platforms (April 5, 2023). By utilizing digital platforms, businesses can easily connect with various marketplaces and explore opportunities for product distribution and sales. These connections enable businesses to expand their reach and tap into new customer segments, ultimately driving growth and profitability.

In summary, the interviews suggest that digital platforms offer entrepreneurs the ease of market identification and access. Through digital channels, businesses can reach a wider audience, establish partnerships, and enjoy the benefits of convenient and accessible marketing. The seamless connections and collaborations made possible by digital platforms contribute to the success and growth of businesses in the digital era.

Advantages of Digital Platforms

The advantages of digital platforms in product marketing are evident from the interviews conducted. Irsyad Adi Putra mentions that 20% of his buyers come from digital platforms, highlighting the effectiveness and reach of these channels (interviewed on March 25, 2023). This statistic emphasizes the potential customer base that can be tapped into through digital marketing, showcasing the advantages of utilizing these platforms for business growth.

Arfan, the owner of Black White Coffee, acknowledges the potential difficulties faced by businesses that do not utilize digital means (interviewed on March 15, 2023). This suggests that digital platforms provide a competitive edge and enable businesses to stay connected with their target audience. By leveraging digital channels, businesses can overcome geographical barriers, reach a larger audience, and promote their products more effectively.

Ilham Maulana highlights the versatility of digital platforms in managing product markets (interviewed on April 5, 2023). He mentions that consumer age structure and preferences can be taken into account, similar to traditional marketing methods such as banners, billboards, or newspaper promotions. This indicates that digital platforms offer the same level of targeting and personalization capabilities as traditional advertising channels, if not more. By leveraging digital marketing strategies, businesses can tailor their messages and offerings to specific consumer segments, increasing the effectiveness of their marketing efforts.

Additionally, the interviews suggest that the food industry, in particular, benefits from digital platforms by creating stronger cravings among potential buyers, even those who may not initially be inclined to consume a specific product. This highlights the power of digital marketing in influencing consumer behavior and generating interest in products or services.

In summary, the advantages of digital platforms in product marketing include increased reach, effective targeting, and the ability to create strong consumer cravings. By utilizing digital channels, businesses can tap into a wider customer base, tailor their marketing efforts, and influence consumer behavior to drive sales and business growth.

Table 2: Lists the Key Informant Interviews Conducted By Saripati, As Well As the Categories, Patterns, and Concepts Related To the First Study Issue

Research Problems	Informant	Category/ Strategy	Patterns and Concepts
Question 1. What business steps/strategies are taken by MSME owners?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic location • Facilities provided 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic location • Facilities prepared 	In the business undertaken by MSMEs, namely determining strategic locations and easy to reach. Also prepare facilities in the form of chairs to wait for orders to be made
Question 2. What steps/strategies have MSME owners taken in this disruptive era?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovative • An affordable price • Meet directly with consumers. • Communication that good with consumers. • Instill a hard working attitude 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost leadership • Differentiation • Focus 	In terms of sales strategy, MSMEs implement a cost leadership strategy where this strategy is very effective in conditions of price competition between buying and selling. Furthermore, MSMEs also apply a differentiation strategy which is considered very effective for companies that have a scope of competition, and try to reach consumers by offering products that are different from competitors. MSMEs also apply a focus strategy to develop their business when the target market segment is increasing and growing.

Source: Results of interviews with informants, 2023

The interview results indicate an increase in consumer interaction, convenience, and cost savings through digital means. They are able to save on promotion costs and continuously update information. Digital platforms that present various types of technology-based marketing media for specific products produced by MSMEs have been designed and developed (Salim et al., 2023).

The interview findings and discussions from the informants above can conclude that digital platforms provide ease of collaboration with partners on digital platforms due to their wide reach, fast connections, and availability of images and videos that can visualize products or provide supporting presentations. Research has also designed digital platforms for MSMEs per administrative region (Purwana et al., 2018). (Haenlein & Kaplan, 2019), define social media as a group of internet-based applications built on the ideology and technological foundation of Web 2.0 and enabling the creation and exchange of user-generated content. The informants

experienced increased revenue, and the community became more aware of the products they market due to the number of people accessing social networks anytime and anywhere. They can access computers and mobile phones with effective and efficient marketing communication.

The findings of this study can be understood that SMEs, which generally have small business sizes, have less capacity to behave unethically compared to large companies (Spence, 1999). The role of knowledge can serve as the basis for creating competitive advantage, supported by resource-based theory (Grant, 1996). Knowledge-based views are essential elements in driving the creation of organizations with dynamic capabilities, where organizations act as containers for the application of knowledge collected by their members (Spender, 1996). Forms of knowledge and their applications are diverse, both in large and small companies. This study seeks to investigate the role of knowledge at the Small-Medium Enterprise (SME) level as one of the main drivers of organizational advancement. Small businesses that rely on entrepreneurial activities are highly dependent on creative survival. As economic supporters, micro, small, and medium enterprises should be empowered to enhance the quality of economic growth and are expected to be a solution to economic disparities.

Based on the study's results, it is concluded that MSMEs in Makassar City have effectively utilized digital platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and marketplaces and have experienced increased consumer interest. MSMEs can harness the influence of digital media if done optimally in terms of the duration of promotion and the development of marketing strategies. Further studies can be enhanced by incorporating digital aspects into government decision-making. This action can explain the level of absorption in policy sectors to accommodate digital needs. Potential efforts can also explore from various demographic structure perspectives. They could involve different genders, positions within the family, educational levels, political tendencies, and other beneficial paths. We leave this to future research endeavors.

CONCLUSION

1. The strategies employed by MSMEs to survive in the disruptive era, especially in their sales, include using cost leadership strategy, product differentiation strategy, market opportunity-focused strategy, and customer proximity strategy. They also emphasize the values of hard work and effective communication in fulfilling customer orders. During their business operations, entrepreneurs acquire customers through social media platforms or marketplaces and engage in word-of-mouth marketing, where satisfied customers refer the business to others based on their own initiative.
2. Further studies can be improved by incorporating digital aspects into government decision-making on a massive scale. This action can explain the level of absorption in policy sectors to accommodate digital needs. Potential efforts can also explore various perspectives of demographic structures. These may include different genders, positions within the family, educational levels, political tendencies, and other beneficial factors. We leave these areas for future research endeavors.

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